

Global Stability Analysis for Shock Buffet in a Transonic Axial Flow Fan

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OBJECTIVES

Global Stability Analysis, Transonic buffet, Unsteady Aerodynamics, RANS.

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

With advancements in computational power and numerical methods, global stability analysis (GSA) has been a powerful tool for studying flow instabilities. Techniques like the Krylov methods employing the shift-and-invert strategy—Krylov-Schur (1) and ARPACK (2)—have made it possible to solve large-scale eigenvalue problems associated with realistic wing geometries. GSA stands out for its ability to provide detailed quantitative and qualitative insights into the mechanisms of transonic shock buffet. Shock buffet, or shock oscillation due to shock-boundary layer interaction in transonic flows, is an important phenomenon of particular interest for researchers. Shock oscillation imparts time-varying loads on aerospace structures which has the potential to lead to fatigue-induced failure.

The comprehensive perspective on flow behavior, predictive capabilities, versatility of GSA, and its provision of integration with computational methods make it a superior tool for researchers aiming to understand and mitigate shock buffet in aerodynamic applications. GSA involves examining the linear

stability of a base flow to understand the onset and development of flow instabilities. It uses the Navier-Stokes equations linearized around a steady or time-averaged (mean) flow solution. By solving the eigenvalue problem, resulting from the linearization, one can identify unstable modes and their growth rates, providing insights into the mechanisms driving flow instabilities. Crouch, *et al.* (3) predicted the onset of shock buffet on NACA0012 using GSA based on steady solutions of the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations. Sartor *et al.* (4) reproduced shock buffet on the OAT15A super-critical airfoil as an unstable global mode from a steady base flow. Crouch, *et al.* (5) used global stability analysis to predict the onset of transonic buffet on infinite swept and unswept wings. For the unswept wing, they reported presence of stationary modes in addition to oscillatory mode observed on 2D airfoils. For the swept wing, they found the stationary modes becoming traveling modes and propagating outboard along the wing. Using a biglobal stability analysis, Paladini *et al.* (6) tried to explain the evolution of the transonic buffet phenomenon from two-dimensional airfoils to three-dimensional swept wings. Their study on infinite wings found that the frequency for airfoil (2D) buffet mode increases up to an order of magnitude higher for a particular sweep angle when compared to that for an upswept wing. Timme (7) studied the shock buffet on a finite three-dimensional wing, the NASA Common Research Model (CRM), using GSA and identified features of shock buffet that are distinct from that reported on infinite wings. Using a triglobal stability analysis, Timme and He (8) report presence of airfoil buffet modes on finite span unswept wings along with monotone (non-oscillatory) or spatially periodic shock-distortion modes. They further found the monotone modes traveling outboard on swept wings. Sansica and Hashimoto (9) presented a Jacobian-free method for carrying out GSA and predicted turbulent transonic shock buffet on the NASA CRM. They also report existence of buffet cells at flight Reynolds numbers.

While there is an appreciable amount of literature available on the use of global stability analysis on wing-sections and wings—unswept and swept—to study shock buffet, there is hardly any in the realm of turbomachinery. In the current work, we

present a general framework for global stability analysis utilizing an open source numerical fluid flow simulation code and an open source scalable eigenvalue solver. The prognostic potential of the global stability analysis method devised is assessed by predicting shock buffet over a transonic axial flow fan.

METHODOLOGIES

Numerical method for fluid flow simulation

We have used the SU2 (Stanford University Unstructured) suite of CFD codes (10; 11) for solving Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations. The system of governing equations in conservative form for a domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ in compressible viscous flow is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}_c - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}_v - \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad t > 0. \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{U} = [\rho, \rho \mathbf{q}, \rho E]^T$ is the vector of conservative variables with ρ denoting the fluid density, \mathbf{q} is the flow velocity in the rotating frame of reference, and E is the relative total energy per unit mass (12; 13). \mathbf{F}_c is the vector of convective fluxes, \mathbf{F}_v is the vector of viscous fluxes and \mathbf{Q} is the vector of source terms in the rotating frame of reference given by

$$\mathbf{F}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \mathbf{q} \\ \rho \mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{q} + \bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}} p \\ \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}_v = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \bar{\bar{\tau}} \\ \bar{\bar{\tau}} \cdot \mathbf{q} + \mu_{tot} c_p \nabla T \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{and} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \rho(\mathbf{f} + \mathbf{f}_{cor} + \mathbf{f}_{cent}) \\ \rho \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{q}_H \end{bmatrix}$$

with $\mathbf{I} = h + \frac{q^2}{2} - \frac{u^2}{2}$ denoting the rothalpy for systems referenced in a rotating frame where, h is the enthalpy of the system and $\mathbf{u} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}$ is the entrainment velocity, $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ and \mathbf{r} being the rotational speed of the rotating frame and the position vector respectively, and $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}}$ is the unit tensor and p is the pressure. $\mu_{tot} = \frac{\mu_{lam}}{Pr_{lam}} + \frac{\mu_{tur}}{Pr_{tur}}$ is the non-dimensional viscosity, Pr_{lam} and Pr_{tur} being the laminar and turbulent Prandtl numbers respectively, and c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure and T is the temperature. The turbulent viscosity μ_{tur} is derived using a suitable turbulence model. The viscous stress tensor $\bar{\bar{\tau}}$ is given as

$$\bar{\bar{\tau}} = \mu_{tot} \left(\nabla \mathbf{q} + \nabla \mathbf{q}^T - \frac{2}{3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} \bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The term \mathbf{f} is the external force (per unit volume) vector and the additional terms $\mathbf{f}_{cor} = -2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{q})$ and $\mathbf{f}_{cent} = -\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$

are the Coriolis and centrifugal forcing terms respectively that appear when the frame of reference is rotating with an angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$, and \mathbf{q}_H is the external heat source. The corresponding equations for non-rotating or stationary problems can be deduced by setting the rotational speed to zero. The pressure is related to the velocities and energy through the equation of state.

The system of partial differential equations governing the fluid flow presented in Eq. 1 is solved using a cell-vertex based finite volume scheme (13). A scalar upwind scheme is used for the spatial discretization of the flow domain and the Roe upwind scheme (14) is used for calculating the inviscid flux at the interfaces. Second-order MUSCL reconstruction is achieved using the van Albada limiter (15). The viscous terms are discretized using an average-gradient formulation. The gradients are evaluated using a least-square method (12). A CFL number of 10 is used for the pseudo time stepping in arriving at the steady flow solution. The Euler implicit method is used for time integration of the temporally discretized equations following the spatial discretization. The generalized minimum residual (GMRES) method which approximates the solution by the vector in a Krylov subspace with minimal residual, found by Arnoldi iteration, is used for the linear solver. An incomplete lower-upper (ILU) factorization scheme is used for pre-conditioning the linear solver. The Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model with Edwards and Chandra's correction (16) and compressibility correction (17) is used for turbulence closure. The choice of this variant of the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model is driven by the fact that transonic buffet on supercritical airfoils (18; 19) and on three-dimensional fixed wing (20) is successfully simulated using the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model with the Edwards and Chandra's correction that improves the near-wall behavior.

Global stability analysis procedure

Global stability analysis involves investigation of the behavior of a steady or mean flow field, also known as base flow, upon introduction of small three-dimensional perturbations, in terms of growth or decay of the resulting flow field. The governing Eq. 1, after spatial discretization, can be written as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}}{dt} = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{U}) \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{R} is the residual vector. If there exists a base flow \mathbf{U}_b , then $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{U}_b) = 0$ as the base flow is stationary by definition. To assess the stability of the base flow, a small perturbation \mathbf{U}' is applied to the base flow \mathbf{U}_b so that the resulting perturbed flow is $\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U}_b + \mathbf{U}'$. After linearizing the discretized Eq. 4 to first order, the governing equation for the perturbation can be written as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}'}{dt} = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{U}' \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{J} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial \mathbf{U}}|_{\mathbf{U}=\mathbf{U}_b}$ is the Jacobian corresponding to the linearization of the residual \mathcal{R} around the base flow \mathbf{U}_b . Assuming a solution of the form $\mathbf{U}'(x, y, z, t) = \widehat{\mathbf{U}}(x, y, z)e^{\lambda t}$, Eq. 5 can be written as an eigenvalue problem as follows.

$$\mathbf{J}\widehat{\mathbf{U}} = \lambda\widehat{\mathbf{U}} \quad (6)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{U}}$ are the global modes and $\lambda = \sigma + i\omega$ are the eigenvalues, σ and ω representing the growth rate and angular frequency of the global modes respectively. The base flow becomes unstable when at least one of the global modes exhibits a positive growth rate.

TABLE 1: Key specifications of NASA rotor 67

Number of blades	22
Design mass flow rate	33.25 kg/s
Design pressure ratio	1.63
Design rotational speed	16043 rev/min
Rotor tip speed	429 m/s
Design tip clearance	0.001016 m
Inlet tip relative Mach number	1.38
Aspect ratio (average span/root axial chord)	1.56
Solidity at tip	1.29
Solidity at hub	3.11
Hub/tip radius ratio at inlet	0.375
Hub/tip radius ratio at exit	0.478
Tip diameter at inlet	0.514 m
Tip diameter at exit	0.485 m

Elements of the Jacobian corresponding to a stencil usually depend only on the variables within the immediate neighborhood of the particular stencil. Thus the Jacobian is usually a sparse matrix. The global Jacobian matrix is extracted from the SU2 solver. Details of the formulation of the Jacobian in SU2 can be found in Ref. (10). The eigenvalue problem Eq. 6 is solved using the open source SLEPc ([Scalable Library for Eigenvalue Problem Computations](#)) tool which utilizes the PETSc ([Portable, Extensible Toolkit for Scientific Computation](#)) routines. The Jacobian matrix extracted using SU2 is partitioned using SLEPc routines and parsed into a PETSc eigensolver built with complex architecture.

TABLE 2: Flow boundary conditions

Boundary	Description
Inlet	Total Pressure = 101325 Pa Total Temperature = 288.15 K
Outlet	Static pressure/back pressure
Solid walls	No slip adiabatic wall

FIGURE 1: Meridional view of rotor 67 and aerodynamic survey locations (21).

The Krylov-Schur (1) algorithm is used for solving the eigenvalue problem with a shift-and-invert strategy. In this algorithm, which is a computationally efficient algorithm to find a few eigenvalues for large problems in the vicinity of a given eigenvalue, a shift is first applied to the Jacobian matrix. The resulting shifted matrix is then inverted and the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of that matrix are evaluated. The eigenvectors obtained thus also represent the eigenvectors for the actual Jacobian matrix, whereas the eigenvalues for the actual Jacobian matrix are obtained by back substitution from the eigenvalues obtained for the shifted and inverted matrix. The distributed direct sparse lower-upper (LU) solver MUMPS ([MULTifrontal Massively Parallel sparse direct Solver](#)) is employed for matrix inversion.

The NASA rotor 67—a low aspect ratio transonic axial flow fan—is chosen as the test case for carrying out the investigations

of this work. Experimental data for steady-state performance (rotor-only) including geometry details are available in (21; 22). The basic design specifications for the rotor 67 are given in **Table 1**. The meridional view of the configuration and aerodynamic survey locations (AERO STATIONS 1 and 2), where relevant flow variables are sampled for evaluating the fan performance parameters (21), are shown in **Figure 1**. The flow boundary conditions for the chosen test case, taken from (21), are presented in **Table 2**.

FIGURE 2: Computational domain for NASA rotor 67

MAIN RESULTS

Strazisar et al. (23) reported shock oscillations in the NASA rotor 67 fan across a range of operating points on the fan performance map. While Ref. (23) estimated the shock excursion in the transonic fan using laser anemometry test data, it fell short in describing necessary attributes of shock buffet including the buffet frequency. Recently, Majhi and Venkatraman (24; 25) predicted shock buffet in the NASA rotor 67 using URANS. The authors reported shock buffet at two operating points on the fan performance map—near design mass flow and towards stall. For the operating point near design mass flow they report a shock excursion of about 2% fan chord at 70% and 90% span-wise locations with a buffet frequency of 385 Hz. The buffet frequency corresponds to $St = 0.076$ based on the chord length and relative velocity at the tip section.

Figure 2 shows the computational domain used in this work for the NASA rotor 67. The computational domain used here

FIGURE 3: Comparison of coarser and RANS grids

is exactly the same as that was used by the authors in Ref. (25) for predicting shock buffet using URANS. The inlet of the computational domain is located at an axial location one and a half times the axial chord upstream of the blade leading edge at the hub and the outlet is chosen to be at an axial location twice the axial chord downstream of the blade trailing edge at the hub. The authors used a grid based on HOH topology with a cell count of about 18 million for the full annulus in the URANS simulations for predicting shock buffet in Ref. (25).

The resulting Jacobian matrix for the full-annulus model of the axial flow fan used in Ref. (25) consisting of the contributions of the six conserved variables— ρ , ρu , ρv , ρw , ρE and $\rho \tilde{v}$ —has a dimension of about 102 million and has about 3013 million non-zero elements. Solving for eigenvalues of a matrix of this size would certainly lead to a very large memory requirement. While such memory requirements can certainly be fulfilled by the state of art computing resources, it surely invites other viable means to do away with such requirements. One workaround is to use a coarser level of discretization of the flow solution which would lead to a Jacobian matrix of a comparatively smaller size. To achieve this, a coarser grid is generated following the same topology that was used for generating the grid which was used in the RANS and URANS simulations in Ref. (25). The steady flow solution obtained using the grid of Ref. (25), which is the base flow here, is then mapped onto the coarser grid. Subsequently, the Jacobian matrix of the coarser grid, with the interpolated steady flow solution from the grid used in Ref. (25), is formed using SU2, and global stability analysis is carried out. This is a common workaround, reported in literature in references (26; 27), for carrying out global stability analysis. It is to be noted that here the coarser grid is not used for carrying out any RANS simulation, and the RANS solution obtained using an optimum grid, which is

validated against test data in Ref. (25), is used as the base flow in this process. This process certainly requires an additional grid to be generated, but it drastically brings the computational resource requirement down to a much more accessible level.

The coarse grid using the HOH-grid topology, that was used for generating the RANS/URANS grid in Ref. (25), is generated using NUMECA Autogrid5 Academic software. A single passage of the coarser grid has about 0.13 million cells which makes the full-annulus grid to have about 2.87 million cells and about 3.05 million nodes. The grid used in Ref. (25) for predicting shock buffet was having about 0.81 million cells per passage, and 18 million cells for the whole wheel. A picture of the coarse grid containing one blade and the hub spanning one passage is shown in Fig. 3 along with that for the grid used in Ref. (25) for comparison. The steady flow (RANS) solution obtained in Ref. (25), corresponding to the operating point near design mass flow rate, is interpolated onto the coarse grid. The quality of the interpolation of the solution is verified by visually comparing contours of few flow variables at a few span-wise stations. Figure 4 presents a comparison of the mapped pressure contours at 70% span location on the coarser grid against that obtained from RANS solution in Ref. (25). Some more checks of the interpolation comparing contours of pressure and density at 70% and 90% span locations on the two grids are included in Appendix. These comparisons indicate a fairly acceptable interpolation of the steady flow solution from the RANS grid onto the coarse grid.

The interpolated steady flow solution on the coarse grid is taken as the base flow for the global stability analysis. The global Jacobian matrix corresponding to the six conserved variables— ρ , ρu , ρv , ρw , ρE and $\rho \tilde{v}$ —is extracted using SU2. The Jacobian matrix has a dimension of ~ 18.3 million and ~ 519 million non-zero elements. The global stability analysis is simulated on a cluster based on 48-core Intel Xeon Cascade Lake 82682.9 GHz processors with 768 GB RAM/node. Using the procedure for carrying out global stability analysis as described in the earlier section, a few eigenvalues in the neighborhood of $St = 0.076$, which corresponds to the shock buffet frequency near the design mass flow operating point as reported in Ref. (25), are evaluated. Twenty eigenvalues are requested using a subspace size of 40 and 27 eigenvalues are converged to a tolerance of 1.0×10^{-8} after 1000 iterations. The simulation took about 19 hours and 13 minutes of wall clock time with 768 processors.

Figure 5 shows the eigenvalues obtained in the vicinity of $St = 0.076$ using the global stability analysis. The eigenvalue encircled in red color in Fig. 5 corresponds to $St = 0.076$ which is also the guess value for the global stability analysis. This eigenvalue is an unstable global mode as it bears a positive growth rate. The eigenmodes at 70% span location corresponding to the unstable global mode are shown in Fig. 6. Figure 6a shows the unstable global mode corresponding to ρ . The three components of the eigenmodes corresponding to the conserved variables representing the momentum— ρu , ρv , ρw —are transformed into

components in a cylindrical co-ordinate system with ρw representing the axial component, ρv_θ representing the circumferential component and ρv_r representing the radial component.

The eigenmodes at 70% span location corresponding to the unstable global mode are shown in Fig. 6. Figure 6a shows the unstable global mode corresponding to ρ . The three components of the eigenmodes corresponding to the conserved variables representing the momentum— ρu , ρv , ρw —are transformed into components in a cylindrical co-ordinate system with ρw representing the axial component, ρv_θ representing the circumferential component and ρv_r representing the radial component. The eigenmodes for the unstable global mode corresponding to ρw , ρv_θ , and ρv_r are shown in Fig. 6b through Fig. 6d. The eigenmodes corresponding to ρE and $\rho \tilde{v}$ are shown in Fig. 6e and Fig. 6f respectively. The sonic lines are also shown in these figures for reference.

From the figures corresponding to all the convective conserved variables, it can be seen that most of the instability starts apparently after the shock locations which indicates shock is driving the instability. In Ref. (25), the shock structure for this axial fan was described in detail which comprised of a detached bow shock, lip shocks, and a passage shock. Moreover, for the operating point near the design mass flow, the bow shock and the passage shock were seen to be merging inside the passage. From the eigenmodes corresponding to ρ and ρE , as shown in Fig. 6a and Fig. 6e respectively, unsteadiness emanating from the three types of shock fronts—bow, lip, and passage—can be clearly seen. An animation of the unsteady eigenmode corresponding to ρE displaying these observations is included in the presentation. Eigenmode corresponding to the axial component of momentum, ρw , shown in Fig. 6b, indicates that higher unsteadiness is seen near the foot of the shock, in the growing boundary layer, compared to other circumferential location of the shock, which was also found from URANS simulation corresponding to this operating point and was reported in Ref. (25).

There is no circumferential periodicity observed in these eigenmodes, which can be seen from the eigenmodes corresponding to ρv_θ , shown in Fig. 6c, as well as other conserved variables. The spatial structure of the unsteadiness is seen to vary from passage to passage, that is, flow structures in different passages are located at varying distances from the shock front. These observations, along with the chunk of unsteady flow structure downstream of the bow shock near the pressure surfaces seen especially in the eigenmode corresponding to ρv_θ , indicate of certain phase difference between the unsteady flow in adjacent passages. This finding is in a qualitative agreement with the finding reported from the URANS simulation (25) that suggested an almost out-of-phase relationship between the shock motions in adjacent passages, although the global stability analysis here has not been able to accurately quantify the phase difference.

From the eigenmode corresponding to the conserved variable corresponding to turbulence closure, $\rho \tilde{v}$, shown in Fig. 6f, most of

the unsteadiness is seen to be appearing around the bow shock and after the passage shock. The unsteadiness arising from the bow shock seems to be convecting down on the suction surface and interacting with the passage shock. Further, unsteadiness arising from the suction side of each blade is seen to be interacting with that arising from the pressure side of the lagging blade within and beyond the corresponding passage.

The eigenmodes at 90% span location corresponding to the unstable global mode are presented in the Appendix. Similar behaviors of the eigenmodes are observed at 90% span location as those observed at 70% span location. However, as this span location is very close to the tip (and shroud) where the flow is more unsteady compared to that at 70% span, the eigenmodes at this span location are slightly smeared out compared to those seen at 70% span.

In summary, then, the devised global stability analysis framework is able to predict the frequency of the shock buffet at the chosen operating point of the axial flow fan very accurately. The eigenmodes of individual conserved variables corresponding to the unstable global mode predicted from the global stability analysis capture many of the salient attributes of the unsteady flow field predicted using URANS utilizing a fraction of the computational resources used for the URANS simulation.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, global stability analysis is performed, perhaps for the first time, in order to predict shock buffet in a turbomachine consisting of a 3D, full-annulus model of a rotating axial flow fan. This global stability analysis framework utilizes an open source numerical fluid flow simulation code and an open source scalable eigenvalue solver. Starting with a steady flow solution as a base flow, transonic shock buffet is predicted for the axial flow fan at an operating point near its design mass flow and valuable insights of buffet flow are interpreted through visualization of the modeshapes of flow variables corresponding to the unstable global mode. The buffet frequency is predicted very accurately. The eigenmodes corresponding to the unstable global mode shows that most of the unsteadiness appears from the various shock fronts associated with the transonic flow. The transonic flow over the axial fan has a distinct shock structure consisting of mainly three types of shocks—bow, lip, and passage. The unsteadiness emanating from the shock fronts indicate that the instability is driven by shock oscillation. Further, the buffet mode-shapes predicted by the global stability analysis indicate that there is no circumferential flow periodicity in the buffet flow and there is a certain phase difference between the shock motions in adjacent passages as reported in the literature, although the method used here is not able to accurately quantify that phase difference.

Appendix: Interpolation of results from RANS grid onto coarse grid

Contours of pressure at 90% span on the coarse grid interpolated from the RANS grid are compared with that on RANS grid in Fig. 7. Interpolated density contours on the coarse grid and density contours on the RANS grid are compared at 70% span and 90% span in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively.

The eigenmodes of ρ , ρw , ρv_θ , ρv_r , ρE and $\rho \tilde{v}$ components corresponding to the unstable global mode at 90% span location are presented in Fig. 10.

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(a) Coarser grid for GSA

(b) RANS grid

FIGURE 4: Comparison of pressure contours for coarse and medium-density grids at 70% span

FIGURE 5: Eigen spectrum in the vicinity of buffet frequency

(a) Eigenmode corresponding to ρ

(d) Eigenmode corresponding to ρv_r

(b) Eigenmode corresponding to ρw

(e) Eigenmode corresponding to ρE

(c) Eigenmode corresponding to ρv_θ

(f) Eigenmode corresponding to $\rho \tilde{v}$

FIGURE 6: Unstable global (buffet) mode for rotor 67 at 70% span (*continued*)

FIGURE 6: Unstable global (buffet) mode for rotor 67 at 70% span

(a) Coarse grid for GSA

(b) RANS grid

(a) Coarse grid for GSA

(b) RANS grid

FIGURE 7: Comparison of pressure contours for coarse and RANS grids at 90% span

FIGURE 8: Comparison of density contours for coarse and RANS grids at 70% span

(a) Coarse grid for GSA

(b) RANS grid

FIGURE 9: Comparison of density contours for coarse and RANS grids at 90% span

(a) Eigenmode corresponding to ρ

FIGURE 10: Unstable global (buffet) mode for rotor 67 at 90% span

(b) Eigenmode corresponding to ρw

(c) Eigenmode corresponding to ρv_θ

(d) Eigenmode corresponding to ρv_r

(e) Eigenmode corresponding to ρE

(f) Eigenmode corresponding to $\rho \tilde{v}$

FIGURE 10: Unstable global (buffet) mode for rotor 67 at 90% span (*continued*)

FIGURE 10: Unstable global (buffet) mode for rotor 67 at 90% span (*continued*)